

the case of the determination of Nb^{5+} in presence of V^{5+} , Ta^{5+} , ($V^{5+} + Ta^{5+}$) or in presence of mixture containing Ag^+ , Cu^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Hg_2^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , and 10.05 (in the case of the determination of Ta^{5+} in presence of V^{5+} , Nb^{5+} , ($V^{5+} + Nb^{5+}$) or in presence of the other ingredients) using blank solution containing the same [bipy] as in the test solution.

Results and Discussion

The results obtained reveal that V^{5+} can be determined spectrophotometrically at pH 10.36 in presence of Nb^{5+} , Ta^{5+} , Co^{2+} , Sn^{2+} and Fe^{2+} at 220 nm, Al^{3+} , Th^{4+} and Mo^{6+} at 225, and in presence of Al^{3+} and Th^{4+} at 250 nm without interference, whereas Mn^{2+} , Sc^{3+} , La^{3+} , Zr^{4+} and Cr^{6+} positively interfere.

Niobium can be determined in presence of equal or variable $[V^{5+}]$, $[Ta^{5+}]$, mixture of them or admixture of V^{5+} , Ta^{5+} , Fe^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Th^{4+} , Cr^{6+} , Mo^{6+} and W^{6+} at 230, 235 and 275 nm without interference, while Ag^+ , Cu^{2+} , Hg_2^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Sc^{3+} , Y^{3+} , La^{3+} , Sn^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Ti^{4+} , In^{3+} , U^{6+} , Mn^{2+} and Fe^{3+} seriously interfere.

Tantalum can be assayed in presence of equal or variable $[V^{5+}]$, $[Nb^{5+}]$, mixture of them or admixture of Co^{2+} , Sn^{2+} (220, 225 and 250 nm), Th^{4+} and Mo^{6+} (225 nm), W^{6+} , Al^{3+} and Al^{3+} (210 nm) without interference. Ag^+ , Cu^{2+} , Hg_2^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Sc^{3+} , Y^{3+} , La^{3+} , Ti^{4+} , Zr^{4+} , U^{6+} , Mn^{2+} , Bi^{3+} , Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} seriously interfere and underrate the determination of Ta. The method is simple, sensitive, accurate and useful for the determination of trace amounts (ppb ppm) of V^{5+} , Nb^{5+} and Ta^{5+} .

References

1. I. M. ISSA, R. M. ISSA and R. M. AWADALLAH, *Egypt. J. Chem.*, 1975, 18, 801.
2. M. K. SHERIF, R. M. AWADALLAH and F. S. MOHAMED, *Bull. Fac. Sci. Assiut Univ. Egypt*, 1978, 7, 461.
3. M. K. SHERIF, R. M. AWADALLAH and F. S. MOHAMED, *Bull. Fac. Sci. Assiut Univ. Egypt*, 1978, 7, 371.
4. R. M. AWADALLAH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 685.
5. H. N. FURMAN, "Standard Methods of Chemical Analysis", 6th ed., Van Nostrand, 1966.
6. J. ROSIN, "Reagent Chemical and Standards", 5th ed., Van Nostrand, 1967.
7. H. T. S. BRITTON, "Hydrogen Ions", 4th ed. 1956.

Tris(2,2'-Dipyridyl) Iron(II) and Ethyl Orange as Indicators for the Titration of Vanadium(IV) with Cerium(IV) Sulphate

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THE reaction of vanadium(IV) with cerium(IV) in dilute sulphuric acid was considered slow in the light of the elevated temperature condition recommended for the potentiometric titration^{1,2}.

A recent study³, however, shows that the main reaction is fast, and that the difficulty is due to slow potential equilibration of vanadium system at the platinum electrode. It has been found that the titration can be done at room temperature to a potentiometric or visual end point, provided phosphoric acid is used as catalyst^{4,5}. The use of ferroin as internal indicator for this titration was investigated without success⁶. Later, ferroin indicator was successfully used⁷ by employing a titration medium of acetic acid and sulphuric acid mixture (7-8.5 M + 0.1-0.3 M). Other indicators^{8,9} are also used in such mixed acid medium, but none of them is superior to ferroin. The use of ferroin and some triphenylmethane dyes as indicators in 0.1-0.25 M sulphuric acid for this titration, employing hexacyanoferrate(III) as catalyst, has been reported¹⁰.

Tris (2,2'-dipyridyl) iron(II) is a metal complex of the ferroin type, but is much cheaper¹¹. Its redox potential is reported¹² to be 1.023 V. Despite the fact that the complex is much less stable in acid solutions than ferroin¹², it is successfully used as indicator in titrations of iron(II). We have investigated the use of this indicator in vanadium(IV)-cerium(IV) titration.

Methyl orange¹³ was used as indicator in the titration of vanadium(IV) with cerium(IV) sulphate using 0.5-1.0 M sulphuric acid as titration medium. We have observed that with the use of ethyl orange as indicator the working acid range is improved so much that vanadium(IV) in high acid solutions can be titrated without dilution. Ethyl orange like methyl orange is an irreversible indicator and evidently works in this titration owing to step (i) being faster than step (ii) :

Experimental

Vanadium(IV) solution in 0.25 M sulphuric acid was prepared and standardized by standard method³. Cerium(IV) sulphate solution in 0.25 M sulphuric acid was prepared from commercial cerium(IV) oxide and standardized against BDH AnalaR quality sodium oxalate. The strength of potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) solution was 1% and that of tris (2,2'-dipyridyl)iron(II) sulphate, 0.01 M. Ethyl orange (Chroma-Gesellschaft Schmid & Co.) was 0.5% solution in double distilled water. The indicator solutions have been found to be stable for more than six months.

Titration of vanadium(IV) :

Tris(2,2'-dipyridyl) iron(II) sulphate as indicator : 2.5-10.0 ml vanadium(IV) solution was treated with enough 1.0 M sulphuric acid to give an overall acidity of 0.1-0.25 M near the end point, and diluted to 45 ml. Then 0.5-1.0 ml of potassium

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hexacyanoferrate(III) solution and 2 drops of *tris* (2,2'-dipyridyl) iron(II) sulphate indicator solution were added to it. The mixture was titrated with cerium(IV) sulphate, however, allowing 30-60 sec time gap between the addition of drops towards the close of titration. The end point was marked by a sharp colour change from orange red to yellow. The indicator correction was not needed. The transition potential of the indicator under the titration conditions was found to be 1.13 V vs NHE.

Titration of a mixture of iron(II) and vanadium(IV) solution under similar experimental conditions was found to yield a result that corresponds to the total of iron(II) and vanadium(IV). However, it is necessary to add the catalyst, hexacyanoferrate(III) only after the complete oxidation of iron(II) to avoid a blue precipitate of Prussian blue.

Ethyl orange as indicator: 2.5-10.0 ml of vanadium(IV) solution was treated with enough 5.0 M sulphuric acid to give an overall acidity of 0.25-3.0 M and diluted to 45 ml. Then 2-3 drops of ethyl orange indicator solution was added and the mixture titrated with cerium(IV) sulphate. The change of colour at the end point was from pink to yellow. The indicator correction was 0.04 ml of 0.05 M cerium(IV) sulphate. The transition potential of the indicator under the titration conditions was found to be 1.30 V vs NHE.

In the presence of iron(II) along with vanadium(IV) in the procedure, the titre corresponds to the total of iron(II) and vanadium(IV).

Analysis of ferro-vanadium: About 1.0 g accurately weighed ferro-vanadium sample was treated with 40 ml sulphuric acid (1 : 1) and 40 ml nitric acid (1 : 1) and heated. When the reaction abated, the solution was evaporated to dense white fumes, cooled to room temperature and diluted with distilled water to 250 ml. A 5.0 ml aliquot was treated with 10 ml 0.05 M iron(II) and enough sulphuric acid (with cooling) to give an overall acidity ~10 M. Two drops of ethyl orange indicator solution were added and the mixture titrated with 0.05 M cerium(IV) sulphate till the complete discharge of pink colour. After the oxidation of excess of iron(II) thus, the content of the flask was diluted with distilled water to make the solution 2.5 M in sulphuric acid. Two drops of ethyl orange indicator solution were again added, and vanadium(IV) content of the solution determined by titration with 0.05 M cerium(IV) sulphate according to the procedure described earlier.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the results of study of interference by foreign ions in both the procedures, using *tris* (2,2'-dipyridyl) iron(II) sulphate and ethyl orange as indicators.

TABLE 1—STUDY OF INTERFERENCES, FOR DETERMINATION OF 13 mg OF VANADIUM(IV)

Interfering ion	Tolerance limit, mg	
	Tris (2,2'-dipyridyl) iron(II) as indicator	Ethyl orange as indicator
Cl ⁻	650	800
NO ₃ ⁻	3,200	3360
PO ₄ ³⁻	100	500
ClO ₄ ⁻	1000	1780
CH ₃ COO ⁻	4900	5150
Cr(III)	125	150
Ni(II)	140	150
Cu(I)	180	200
Zn(II)	400	400
Mn(II)	250	250
Fe(III)	400	400

Some typical results of the determination of vanadium(IV) using the indicators in the titrimetric procedures are provided in Table 2,

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF VANADIUM(IV)

Indicator	Taken, mg	Found, mg	Relative error, %
Tris (2,2'-dipyridyl) iron(II)	6.37	6.35	-0.31
	8.91	8.88	-0.34
	15.28	15.30	+0.13
	20.38	20.40	+0.10
	24.20	24.22	+0.08
Ethyl orange	7.64	7.66	+0.26
	12.74	12.72	-0.16
	17.83	17.78	-0.28
	22.92	22.88	-0.17
	25.47	25.50	+0.12

In developing a procedure for the determination of vanadium in ferro-vanadium advantage is taken of the fact that vanadium(IV) does not interfere in the titration of iron(II) with cerium(IV) sulphate, using ethyl orange as indicator if the titration medium is ~10 M sulphuric acid. Typical results are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—ANALYSIS OF FERRO-VANADIUM

Sample taken	Amount of vanadium, % (certified value)	Amount of vanadium found by the present method, %*
Euro-Standard 577-1		
Ferro-Vanadium (BAS-sample)		
Contents : C, 0.089 ; Si, 1.79 ; Mn, 0.158 ; P, 0.035 ; S, 0.034 ; Ni, 0.053 ; Al, 0.414 ; Cu, 0.054%.	50.16	50.08

*Average of five determinations.

Tris (2,2'-dipyridyl) iron(II) has been found to work as an indicator in the cerimetric titration of vanadium(IV) under such experimental conditions which are generally believed to adversely affect its stability. Hexacyanoferrate(III) is used as catalyst.

Ethyl orange, another indicator recommended for this titration, has the advantage of being used in a high acid medium without the requirement of a catalyst; evidently vanadium(IV)-cerium(IV) reaction must be fast even under these titration conditions.

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References

1. N. H. FURMAN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 1675.
2. H. H. WILLARD and P. YOUNG, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1928, 20, 1972.
3. G. A. RECHNITZ and G. N. RAO, *Anal. Chem.*, 1967, 39, 1192.
4. L. S. A. DIKSHITULU and G. GOPALA RAO, *Talanta*, 1962, 9, 857.
5. G. GOPALA RAO and L. S. A. DIKSHITULU, *Talanta*, 1962, 9, 289.
6. H. H. WILLARD and P. YOUNG, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 3267.
7. K. SRIRAMAM and G. GOPALA RAO, *Talanta*, 1966, 13, 1468.
8. N. VENKATESWARA RAO and V. V. S. ESWARA DUTT, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1970, 250, 192.
9. J. S. GILL and G. N. RAO, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1971, 256, 201.
10. N. VENKATESWARA RAO and V. V. S. ESWARA DUTT, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1970, 51, 563.
11. R. BELCHER, J. N. BRAZIER and W. I. STEPHEN, *Talanta*, 1965, 12, 778.
12. G. H. WALDEN, L. P. HAMMETT and R. P. CHAPMAN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 2649.
13. K. BHASKARA RAO, *Chemist-Analyst*, 1965, 54, 104.

Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Zinc

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LITERATURE indicates that a large number of reagents have been utilized for the spectrophotometric determination of zinc, and several metal ions interfere in the determination¹⁻¹³. Hydroxamic acids have proved to be potential analytical reagents in inorganic and organic analysis¹⁴⁻²⁰. These acids are capable of forming strong and stable 5-membered ring complexes with several metal ions²¹. So far, few data are available for the extraction and spectrophotometric determination of zinc utilizing the hydroxamic acids¹⁶.

In the present investigation a sensitive and selective spectrophotometric method for the determination of zinc is described.

Experimental

The spectral measurements were made on Carl Zeiss Speckol spectrophotometer using 1 cm matched cells. pH measurements were made with Systronics digital pH meter, Model 335 equipped with glass and calomel electrodes.

All the chemicals used were of E. Merck, G. R. grade unless otherwise stated.

N-m-Cl-Phenylpalmitohydroxamic acid (N-m-Cl-PPHA) was synthesized by literature method²² and a 0.1% solution was prepared in chloroform.

A 0.1% solution of 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol (PAN) was prepared in chloroform. A $2.3 \times 10^{-4} M$ zinc solution was prepared by dissolving the requisite amount of zinc sulphate in double distilled water and the zinc content was determined titrimetrically²³.

Procedure : The pH of 2.0 ml zinc solution ($2.3 \times 10^{-4} M$) was adjusted to 8.0 with 0.1 M NH_4OH and 0.1 M NH_4Cl . To this was added 10 ml 0.1% reagent solution, and the contents were shaken vigorously for ~12 min. The phases were allowed to separate and the colourless organic layer extract was separated. The extraction was repeated with 5 ml reagent solution to ensure the complete extraction of zinc. Then 1.0 ml 0.1% PAN solution was added to the combined extract and the volume was made upto 25 ml with chloroform. The absorbance of the dark pink coloured Zn-N-m-Cl-PPHA-PAN complex was measured at 555 nm against a reagent blank, prepared in the same manner.

Results and Discussion

In the present method zinc is first extracted with hydroxamic acid followed by the addition of PAN to the extract. The dark pink coloured mixed complex of Zn-N-m-Cl-PPHA-PAN shows a maximum absorption at 555 nm.

Effect of pH : The effect of pH on the extraction of zinc with N-m-Cl-PPHA was studied in the pH range 1-10.5. It was observed that the extraction commenced after pH 5.0 and was maximum at pH 7.5-10.0 (Table 1). At pH > 10 the extraction decreases. pH 8.0 was chosen for the extraction purposes.

Effect of reagent concentration : A 0.1% solution of N-m-Cl-PPHA is sufficient for complete extraction of zinc.